

Final PhD Thesis Report

PhD 06- PEMbo

**From genotype to
phenotype: patho-
evolution of French strains
of *Mycobacterium bovis*.**

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: INRAE

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards.
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

PhD Report	Final PhD Thesis Report Y5 (2022)
PhD Reference	PEMbo
PhD candidate	CHARLES Ciriac
PhD Lead Supervisor	BOSCHIROLI Maria-Laura
PhD second supervisor	BIET Franck
Other supervisor (s)	MICHELET Lorraine
Due month of the deliverable	M66
Actual submission month	M66
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>This is the default setting. This report will be entirely copied into One Health EJP Work Package 6 Deliverable D6.18 - Thesis Reports of up to 17 PhD studentships.</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders / Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

1. PhD Project team composition

PhD student: CHARLES Ciriac

University at which the PhD is registered: University of Paris Est, France.

Lead PhD Supervisor: BOSCHIROLI Maria-Laura, ANSES, France.

Second Supervisor: BIET Franck, INRAE, France.

Other Supervisors: MICHELET Lorraine, ANSES, France.

2. Abstract

Mycobacterium bovis (*M. bovis*) is the etiological agent of bovine tuberculosis (bTB), a zoonotic disease with a high socioeconomic impact. After having reduced the prevalence of this disease below 0.1% for 6 years, France was recognised bTB free in 2001 which is a very advantageous situation for trading. However, this status is threatened in the recent years by the re-emergence of bTB in some French regions. bTB outbreaks are present in very localized areas and are due to persistent *M. bovis* strains with specific genotypes (defined by spoligotyping and MLVA typing). It is therefore important to understand if among the reasons for bTB increase, genetic factors linked to these dominant genotypes could be included. Furthermore, the transmission link between infected animals (which can involve those of different cattle herds and different wildlife species) remains difficult to establish in regions sharing the same *M. bovis* genotype. Analysis of whole-genome single nucleotide polymorphisms compared with appropriate reference genomes can accurately differentiate field strains. However, new whole genomes closer to the French field strains are needed to perform these studies.

Ten new complete genomes were sequenced using MinION and Illumina technologies. Despite the high stability of *M. bovis* genome, their characterization and comparison allowed a better description of genetic lineages by defining specific genetic criteria for some of them. The use of complete genomes allows a better genomes annotation which improves our knowledge of the genetic diversity of the *M. bovis* genomes. The copy number of an insertion sequence, IS6110, was found to be variable between the different complete genomes. This sequence plays an important role in genome plasticity of the human pathogen *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and was found in high copy numbers in representative genomes of highly prevalent genotypes whereas *M. bovis* is considered to have one or very few copies.

We therefore studied the abundance and location of IS6110 in a larger panel of *M. bovis* genomes representative of the French diversity. These results confirmed that the most persistent genotypes were those with multiple copies of IS6110 and that two of the most common genotypes found in France in recent years present a very high copy number (more than 10). Further studies on 3 important genotypes, SB0120-DHV, SB0120-CO and a sub-group of Cluster A/F4 family, which are respectively found in Dordogne and Haute-Vienne, Côte d'Or and Atlantic Pyrenees (French regions), showed a quite high stability of IS6110 number and their insertion site between host species over 6-to-17-year periods. IS6110-related genetic changes did not appear to occur for host adaptation as suggested for highly prevalent *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains.

This work has improved our knowledge on the *M. bovis* lineages circulating in France and worldwide by establishing a list of genetic characteristics specific to them. Some of these, such as IS6110, seem to be correlated with the epidemiological success of certain genotypes. The new genomes will help to better understand the bTB transmission dynamics in multihost systems and to implement more effective control measures to eradicate the disease in these areas.

3. PhD project self-evaluation

Task 1: Establishment of reference sequences from the main French clonal groups

This task has been achieved successfully. Ciriac has developed a bacterial genomic DNA extraction protocol which has enabled him to obtain DNA of sufficient quantity and quality to perform 3rd generation sequencing of 10 *Mycobacterium bovis* (*M. bovis*) strains with the MinION (Nanopore) technology. Using long read -MinION's data- de novo assembly and short reads -Illumina's data- for genome correction, Ciriac obtained new reference genomes. He developed a pipeline for assemblies. The 10 complete genomes have been submitted to National center for biotechnology information (NCBI) under BioProject accession number PRJNA832544 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA832544/>).

Task 2: Genomic analysis

For this task, Ciriac first worked on several panels of strains already available: the first of 87 genomes representative of French genetic diversity, then three panels of sympatric strains belonging to the current major genotypes. He focused on the IS6110 sequence, an insertion sequence of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex –to which *M. bovis* belongs-, with an important role in genome plasticity and in the bacterium evolution caused by IS6110 transposition. This work was the subject of his first publication (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.891902>) in which he showed that IS6110 is present in multiple copies in endemic French *M. bovis* groups and could lead to phenotypic changes that explain their epidemiologic success. Some IS6110 interrupt or could regulate (with their strong promoter) important genes implied in virulence, host persistence or environmental stress resistance.

Thanks to the new reference genomes, Ciriac was able to carry out further genomic analyses on *M. bovis*. In a second article, a pangenomic study has been performed on the 10 genomes and showed a high similarity between them (<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11010177>). Whole genome SNP (single nucleotide polymorphism) was performed on short read sequencing of the 10 strains in comparison to one of the current *M. bovis* reference genome AF2122, BCG and Mb3601. Pangenome analysis revealed a “closed” pangenome composed of 3900 core genes and only 96 accessory genes. Whole genomes-based alignment using progressive Mauve showed remarkable conservation of the genomic synteny except that the genomes have a variable number of copies of IS6110. Characteristic genomic traits of each lineage were identified through the discovery of specific indels. Altogether, these results provide new genetic features that improve the description of *M. bovis* lineages.

Task 3: Analysis of the antigenic variability: biochemical and lipidomic studies

This task could not be completed. This was partly due to the covid crisis and also to the prolonged closure of the level 3 biosafety laboratory which delayed the completion of the first two tasks. However, the pangenomic analyse realized by Ciriac allowed the identification of genomic events (insertion / deletion or broad sequence polymorphism (LSP)) between the new reference genomes. Possible mutation, deletion or overexpression of a gene have been identified and which will be good molecular targets to be explored. A confirmation of first *in silico* result will be reinforced with an appropriate biochemical or microbiological approach.

4. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD reference	PhD Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered (month)	Comments	Integrative categories*
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-1	First steering committee report	M26	M32	Delay due to the COVID crisis. https://zenodo.org/record/4305724	None*
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-2	Second steering committee report	M39	M39	https://zenodo.org/record/4772558	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-5	Final steering committee	M42	None	This document is not requested by Ciriac's doctoral school.	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-6	Oral communication at a congress	M46	M52	Oral communication on new <i>M. bovis</i> complete genomes study in ABIES doctoral days 2022 congress.	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-7	Publication in an international journal	M46	M53	This deliverable was delayed because writing/correction time and result improvement delayed by COVID-19 crisis. The article is published in Frontiers in Microbiology. https://zenodo.org/record/6821763	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-8	PhD manuscript	M48	M58	French and English version of PhD manuscript have been achieved.	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-9	SHH2020 oral communication	M27	M53	New deliverables add. Oral communication (20min) in French at Maisons-Alfort (France). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581493	None

PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-3.1	ASMOHEJP2020 oral communication	M29	M53	New deliverables add. Oral communication (3min) in English at Prague (Czech republic). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581483	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-10	LABIO AU LABO 2021 event	M37	M53	New deliverables add. Internet event. Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581428	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-11	MT180 2021 oral communication	M38	M53	New deliverables add. 3 minutes thesis competition in French. Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581480	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-12	ASMOHEJP2021 poster 1	M42	M53	New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Copenhagen (Danemark). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581523	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-12.1	ASMOHEJP2021 poster 2	M42	M53	New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Copenhagen (Danemark). Published in Zenodo in embargo: https://zenodo.org/record/6581535	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-12.2	ASMOHEJP2021 oral communication	M42	M53	New deliverables add. Oral communication (3min) at Copenhagen (Danemark). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581468	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-13	SHH 2021 oral communication	M45	M53	New deliverables add. Oral communication (20min) in French at Maisons-Alfort (France). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581474	None

PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-14	JSDA2021 poster	M45	M53	New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Maisons-Alfort (France). Awarded “best poster presentation”. Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581509	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-17	ANSES INTERVIEW 2021	M47	M53	New deliverables add. Internet event. Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581392	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-15	SFM poster 2021	M45	M53	New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Montpellier (France). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581542	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-16	Doc Avenir 2021 oral communication	M45	M53	New deliverables add. Oral communication (10min) in French. Awarded 1 st public price and 2 nd jury price. Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581466	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-18	ASMOHEJP2022 poster	M52	M53	New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Orvieto (Italy). Published in Zenodo in embargo: https://zenodo.org/record/6581531	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-18.1	ASMOHEJP2022 oral communication 1	M52	M53	New deliverables add. Oral communication (3min) in English at Orvieto (Italy). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581461	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-18.2	ASMOHEJP2022 oral communication 2	M52	M53	New deliverables add. Oral communication (5min) in English at Orvieto (Italy). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581451	None

PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-19	M.bovis2022 poster 1	M54	M53	New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Galway (Irlande). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581495	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-19.1	M.bovis2022 poster 2	M54	M53	New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Galway (Irlande). Published in Zenodo in embargo: https://zenodo.org/record/6581503	None
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-E5-20	Second publication in an international journal	M54	M60	https://zenodo.org/record/7533730	None

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

PhD reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	Achieved	Comments
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-1	PacBio + Illumina sequencing for obtaining reference genomes	M30	Yes	M41	Strains are sequenced in MinION technology and two of them are also sequenced in PacBio technology. As planned, all strains are also sequenced in Illumina technology.
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-2	Assembly and annotation of reference genome	M38	Yes	M45	
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-3	Illumina sequencing on supplemental strains	M32	Yes		Three genomes were added to the 7 initial genomes and were sequenced with the same

						sequencing technologies (MinION +Illumina).
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-4	Mapped genome	M36	Yes	M47	
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-5	Strain selection for WP3	M40	Yes	M43	Strains are selected and cultivated to obtain good concentration of them. Moreover the BSL 3 closure put the experiments of WP3 on hold.
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-6	SNP matrix	M44	Yes	M46	SNP matrix was obtain. Complete genome allow to study bacterial genomic structure like the region of difference and broken coding sequence in 10 genomes. These events were also listed and described.
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-7	List of SNP in virulence genes	M44	No	M50	
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-8	Protein profiles	M42	None		This task has not be completed because our Biosafety Level 3 (BSL 3) laboratory was unavailable at the end of the project.
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-9	Lipidomic profiles	M42	None		This task has not be completed because our Biosafety Level 3 (BSL 3) laboratory was unavailable at the end of the project.

5. Interactions with JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.),

None.

6. Interactions with OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

None.

7. Added value and benefits during PhD resulting from being part of the OHEJP doctoral programme and consortium

Being part of the OHEJP consortium allowed me to give an extra dimension to my thesis. It allowed me to get in touch with many other PhD students of the program, opening me to other countries but also to other interesting themes.

The congresses organized by OHEJP also allowed me to challenge myself and present my results to scientists who are not experts in my field. It was very formative for me.

8. Transferrable skills and Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Journée d'accueil des nouveaux doctorants	Introduction of the doctoral school; explanation of the good progress of the thesis during the next three years.	02/10/2019	ABIES
UZH training for working in the NSB3 lab	To learn how to work in a confined type 3 biosecurity lab	31/10/2019	ANSES
MOOC Bioinformatique: algorithmes et génomes	To develop skills in bioinformatics and genome data analysis.	1/11/2019→9/12/2019	MOOC Fun platform
Linux et script pour la bioinformatique	To develop skills in bioinformatics, especially Python.	19/11/2019→21/11/2019	CNRS Montpellier
Bases en épidémiologie des maladies animales et zoonotiques	To learn basic notions on epidemiology. To learn how to set up an epidemiology study. To learn how to use different statistics tests ...	01/12/2019→19/12/2019	MOOC Fun platform
UZH training for working in the molecular biology lab	To understand UZH's molecular biology lab organisation and to evaluate my skills	19/12/2019	ANSES
ADOC - Construire et activer son réseau	To develop skills in professional	20/01/2020	Paris Est university

	presentation and elevator pitch. ADOC give tips to improve your networking.		
Developing Fluency in English: Intermediate - Advanced level in English (B1-C1) session 2	To enhance the students' awareness appropriate vocabulary, pronunciation, intonation and improve their overall confidence in oral communications.	4/02/2020→21/04/2020	Paris Est university
Doc 'Avenir 2020	This was ABIES PhD candidates' annual day, organised by doctoral students to discuss about their future career, and to learn different techniques to help them applying and getting a suitable job. This year, the main subject was about networking and developing a good professional profile	12/02/2020	ABIES
Devenir acteur de la science ouverte : ouvrir ses publications et les déposer dans HAL	To understand concepts and practices in relationship to "open science". To learn how to apply your rights for the deposit of publications in an open archives To learn how to use the HAL interface.	08/07/2020	ABIES
research integrity in Scientific professions (EN and FR)	The objective of this training is to disseminate a culture of research integrity within institutions. Rather than passing on knowledge (this is not a learning process), it is a matter of raising awareness of the various issues associated with research integrity and encouraging a critical approach by proposing the basic elements necessary to understand and support the requirements of research integrity.	05/01/2021	MOOC Fun platform
Ma thèse en 180 secondes	To learn how to explain thesis subject quickly and clearly to a non-scientific people.	11/02/2021	Paris Est University

MinION sequencing training	Presentation of MinION sequencing and how to run it.	22-26/02/2021	ANSES
Bionumerics training	Presentation of Bionumerics	19/04/2021	ANSES
ABIES doctoral days 2021	Scientific meeting on "transition" organised by Ciriac's doctoral school.	6-7/05/2021	Doctoral school ABIES - AgroParisTech
Webinar on bartonella	Knowledge in the detection and treatment of bartonella.	20/05/2021	SFM
Interdisciplinary Seminar 'City and Health: What is the value of the 'One Health' approach for research and action?	Scientific knowledge and exchange on the integration of the Onehealth concept in research and the health system and the need for it to be taken into account at the interdisciplinary and international level.	09/02/2021	Doctoral school ABIES - AgroParisTech
Webinair on legionella	Knowledge in the detection and treatment of legionella.	03/06/2021	SFM
ASMOHEJP2021	Annual scientific meeting of One health European joint programme.	09-10-11/06/2021	One health EJP
Webinair on "useful or useless bacterial serologies "	Webinair on "useful or useless bacterial serologies ".	10/06/2021	SFM
Webinair on measles	Knowledge in the detection and treatment of measles.	24/06/2021	SFM
SARSCoV-2 sequencing with nanopore technology	History of sequencing and bioinformatics analysis. Presentation of the latest tools developed for genome assembly and comparison!	01/07/2021	Doctoral school ABIES - AgroParisTech
Bioinformatic training	One week training at INRAE to confirm genome assembly strategy and refines their analysis.	16-20/08/2021	INRAE
Doc'Avenir 2021	To discover the different possibilities of professional orientation after the thesis.	15/09/2021	Doctoral school ABIES - AgroParisTech
Meeting on « Impact des technologies de rupture : quel rôle des établissements de l'ESR ?»	Knowing the impact of disruptive technologies: what role for reference healthcare institutions.	22-24/09/2021	Doctoral school ABIES - AgroParisTech
Scientific and doctoral days of ANSES 2021	Scientific meeting on: Epidemiology and Surveillance Exposure and toxicology of chemical contaminants Antibiotic resistance Plant health	13,16,20,28 and 30/09/2021	ANSES

	Food safety Animal health and welfare		
Congress of the French Society of Microbiology (SFM) 2021	French scientific meeting on microbiology fields.	22/10/2021	SFM
ASMOHEJP2022	Annual scientific meeting of One health European joint programme of 2022.	11-13/04/2022	One health EJP
Training on Phd thesis writing « Journée de formation à la rédaction du manuscrit – présentiel »	Training on thesis writing and the organisation of the end of the thesis.	20/04/2022	Doctoral school ABIES - AgroParisTech
ABIES doctoral days 2022	Scientific meeting on “one health” organised by Ciriac’s doctoral school.	21-22/05/2022	Doctoral school ABIES - AgroParisTech
<i>M.bovis</i> congress	International scientific meeting on <i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> .	07-10/06/2022	<i>M. bovis</i> 2022 organising committee

9. Ethical Reviews

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<p>Biological samples The beneficiary must confirm that no Human and/or Animal samples will be collected for further analysis.</p> <p>Environmental and Health and Safety (H&S) Aspects The beneficiary must confirm that authorisations for relevant facilities (e.g. security classification of laboratory) have been obtained, and that safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.</p> <p>Non EU countries (<i>putative collaboration with Argentina</i>) The beneficiary must provide details on the material which will be imported to/exported from EU and confirm that the adequate authorisations have been obtained.</p> <p>Please provide more information on Nagoya Protocol Compliance</p>	<p>No human or animal samples will be collected for further analyses</p> <p>Authorisations for relevant facilities have been obtained, and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.</p> <p>Whether any collaboration was established with one of the potential mycobacterial groups in Argentina, INTA-Castelar, the <i>M.bovis</i> French strains to be sent will be so only if a MTA between the two interested parties (Anses-INTA) was signed beforehand and the <i>ad hoc</i> import licence to send them to Argentina was appropriately established. Concerning the Nagoya Protocol in the French territory, within the Framework of the n° 2016-1087 law of the 8 August 2016 for reconquering biodiversity, nature and landscapes, which is the implementation of Nagoya Protocol, the decree n°2017-848 of the 9 May 2017 fixates the rules to have access to the genetic resources situated in the national territory and to share the advantages resulting in their use. Argentina complies with the</p>

	Nagoya protocol by the law 2726 of the 26 November 2015.
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10. Scientific Publications

Publication date	Publication title	Authors	DOI reference	Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? *please specify embargo length	Is it a Gold Open Access?
23/06/2020	IS6110 Copy Number in Multi-Host <i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> Strains Circulating in Bovine Tuberculosis Endemic French Regions	Ciriac Charles, Cyril Conde, Franck Biet, Maria Laura Boschioli and Lorraine Michelet	https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.891902	https://zenodo.org/record/6821763	Yes	Green	
11/01/2023	Features of <i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> Complete Genomes Belonging to 5 Different Lineages	Ciriac Charles, Cyril Conde, Fabien Vorimore, Thierry Cochard, Lorraine Michelet, Maria Laura Boschioli and Franck Biet	https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11010177	A DEFINIR	Yes	Green	

11. Additional Outputs

-la bio au labo: <https://labioaulabo.tumblr.com/post/638210749663232001/ciriac-charles-doctorant-de-deuxi%C3%A8me-ann%C3%A9e-en>

-Ma thèse en 180 secondes : <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NDdasDgzt2Y>

-A day in the life of Ciriac CharlesHARLES: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/a-day-in-the-life-of-ciriac-charles/>

-« Pourquoi la tuberculose bovine persiste dans certaines régions françaises et pas dans d'autres ? » - Portait du doctorant Ciriac Charles : <https://www.anses.fr/fr/content/pourquoi-la-tuberculose-bovine-persiste-dans-certaines-r%C3%A9gions-fran%C3%A7aises>

-Tuberculose bovine : pourquoi certaines souches persistent en France ? : <https://www.anses.fr/fr/tuberculose-bovine-pourquoi-certaines-souches-persistent-en-france>

12. Specific outcomes to highlight in dissemination and communications

None

13. One Health impact

The main objectives of this thesis were to obtain ten new complete genomes of different *M. bovis* clusters and to improve our knowledge of the main genotypes circulating in France. Our work allows us to propose, in addition to AF2122/97 and Mb3601, a complete genome for each main French cluster described above but are also representative of the main clusters present in other countries, they can thus be used as references adapted to these groups in genomic epidemiology studies in order to improve the understanding of *M. bovis* transmission in multi-host systems, among others.

The use of complete genomes during pan-genomic studies allows a better annotation of these and a finer definition of the accessory genome which can be overestimated with the use of fragmented genomes and/or tools that are not adapted.

Despite the high similarity between the different genomes, a number of major genomic events could be identified, some of which are cluster-specific and can be used as their signatures. These data, in addition to the SNPs already found and defined as specific to certain lineages, make it possible to better describe the *M. bovis* clusters present in France, but also in the world. This work is therefore in line with recent work on the classification of *M. bovis*, which aims to propose an operational nomenclature to help comparative genomic studies between different countries.

We showed a correlation between the high copy number of IS6110 in certain strains and the fact that they are representative of certain genotypes that have represented 80% of bovine tuberculosis outbreaks in France for the last 15 years (Cluster A, SB0120-CO and SB0120-DHV). This led us to wonder about the role of IS6110 in the success of these genotypes persisting in very localised regions where bTB is actively circulating. Thus, these multiple insertion sites alone would not explain the persistence of specific genotypes in France or the possibility of adaptation to different animal hosts. Other genetic events, in addition to or alone, could also play a role in the persistence of these strains.

The decrease in the diversity of *M. bovis* strains, described in the literature has drastically reduced the number of genotypes present in France has drastically reduced. Bottlenecks have certainly occurred over time resulting in the fixation of some *M. bovis* genotypes circulating in France today. These strains, persisting today could be due to the national control has not been effective enough to eradicate them locally in regions where they have already existed for a long time (e.g. measures poorly adapted to local epidemiological risk factors). It could also be assumed that they have perpetuated themselves due to improved epidemiological fitness to an environment and their ability to overcome control measures and/or infect their hosts due to phenotypic characteristics acquired after genetic modifications.

14. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>C. Charles' first thesis project steering committee report</i>		
Date:	04/12/2020		
Place:	https://zenodo.org/record/4305724		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	Yes	<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	19	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	

General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	La Bio au labo intervention		
Date:	04/01/2021→08/01/2021		
Place:	Twitter – Facebook - Instagram		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website	Yes	Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public	1800 (Twitter), 600(Facebook) and 200 (Instagram)	Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Ma thèse en 180 secondes
Date:	09/03/2021
Place:	Youtube https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NDdasDgzt2Y
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories	

	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	Yes
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>	Yes	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>	160 during the live and 174 in youtube platform	<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	ABIES doctoral days 2021. Oral presentation.		
Date:	6-7/05/2021		
Place:	Paris France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	

<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>More than 150</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>C. Charles' second thesis project steering committee</i>		
Date:	<i>19/05/2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4772558</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>ASMOHEJP 2021. Speech event.</i>		
Date:	<i>9-10-11/06/2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Visio (Copenhaguen Danemark)</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	<i>Yes</i>

<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>More than 900</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>ASMOHEJP 2021. Presentation of two posters.</i>		
Date:	<i>9-10-11/06/2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Visio (Copenhaguen Danemark)</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>More than 900</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>Scientific Happy Hours. Oral presentation.</i>		
Date:	<i>03/09/2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Teems meeting (Maisons-Alfort France)</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			

	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	Yes
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education,</i>	20	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>Doc'Avenir 2021. Speech competition</i>		
Date:	<i>15/09/2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Paris France</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	Yes
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>More than 50</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	Congress of the French Society of Microbiology (SFM) 2021. Poster presentation.		
Date:	22-24/09/2021		
Place:	Nantes France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	More than 400	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Scientific and doctoral days of ANSES 2021. Poster presentation.		
Date:	13,16,20,28 and 30/09/2021		
Place:	Teems meeting (Maisons-Alfort France)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	More than 170	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	

Policy Makers			
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Name of the activity:	A day in the life of Ciriac Charles		
Date:	09/03/2022		
Place:	https://onehealthjep.eu/a-day-in-the-life-of-ciriac-charles/		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized	Yes
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Don't know	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	ABIES doctoral days 2022. Oral presentation.		
Date:	21-22/04/2022		
Place:	Paris, France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	Number		Number

Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	More than 100	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	ASMOHEJP 2022. Presentation of one poster.		
Date:	11-12-13/04/2022		
Place:	In live (Orvieto Italy) and in Visio		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	More than 900	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	ASMOHEJP 2022. Speech event (RoundTable and Three minute thesis)		
Date:	11-12-13/04/2022		
Place:	In live (Orvieto Italy) and in Visio		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized	
Website		Other	

<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>More than 900</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>M.bovis congress. Presentation of two posters.</i>		
Date:	<i>07-10/06/2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Galway, Ireland</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>500</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>Scientific Happy Hours. Oral presentation.</i>		
Date:	<i>17/06/2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Teems meeting (Maisons-Alfort France)</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	

Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education,	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	ANSES scientific and doctoral days. Short Oral communication.		
Date:	20/10/2022		
Place:	Maisons-Alfort France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education,	200	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	PhD viva		
Date:	25/10/2022		
Place:	Maisons-Alfort France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	

<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>		<i>PhD viva</i>	Yes
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education,</i>	80	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			